

Marriott Security Breach

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1 Introduction

Since officially acquiring Starwood Hotels on September 23, 2016, Marriott International became the world's largest global hospitality company in terms of the number of hospitality properties [1]. Starwood Hotels was well known for its exceptionally flexible hotel loyalty program, the Starwood Preferred Guest (SPG) program, which required complimentary SPG suite upgrades to be granted to members of the highest SPG elite status whenever suites were available.

Following the SPG acquisition, Marriott decided to eliminate all existing SPG and Ritz Carlton accounts and gradually implement a single brand-new hotel loyalty program, the Marriott Bonvoy Program. A couple of months before the official merger of accounts was completed, the ninth-largest security breach of the 21st century was revealed in the system due to an IBM Guardium Alert [2, 4, 5]. The SPG acquisition prompted countless IT department employees to depart from their job roles. Therefore, the breach was not identified due to lax and insufficient monitoring.

Many prominent politicians, government officials, and business executives had achieved the highest SPG elite status by staying at SPG hospitality properties worldwide as they traveled for work regularly. Computer hackers habitually aim to infiltrate such systems to gain unauthorized access to highly confidential and invaluable information, such as passport numbers of government employees and credit card numbers of business executives, and exploit this information for nefarious purposes.

Marriott outsourced the development of the Marriott reservation system to Accenture, an Information Technology company. Coincidentally, SPG also hired Accenture to manage the SPG reservation system. Accenture uncovered the security breach's existence due to a security alert. The security alert was the IBM Guardium Alert, an IBM security solution designed to help entities safeguard data, databases, and data storage of applications [5]. Accenture immediately informed Marriott of the IBM Guardium Alert.

The IBM Guardium Alert was triggered by a database query that was processed to provide details of customers' confidential information [4, 5]. Marriott confirmed that the database query was not initiated by the actual administrative user and that cyber attackers instigated the database query [4, 5]. Marriott immediately hired third-party investigators upon becoming aware of the security breach [4]. Marriott took actions to investigate the root cause, contain the damage, and communicate the security breach details to relevant authorities.

Computer criminals succeeded in installing malware in the system to steal highly confidential information such as passport numbers and credit card numbers of SPG members. Third-party investigators successfully located records of a web shell, a Remote Access Trojan (RAT), and MimiKatz malware that provided computer criminals with unrestricted access and complete control over the hospitality properties reservation system for more than four years [4, 13].

Investigators also uncovered three DMP files and two encrypted files containing passport numbers and credit card numbers of hotel guests [13]. On November 30, 2018, Marriott declared at a press release that records of 500 million hotel guests were leaked; however, later, at another press release on January 4, 2019, Marriott adjusted the number of leaked records to 383 million [4]. Computer criminals had stolen more than 9 million credit card numbers and 24 million passport numbers.

Marriott hired legal representatives to handle the legal implications and class action lawsuits caused by the security breach. Marriott suffered less than £1 million in aggregate financial loss, as they generated enough revenue and profit to cover and offset the loss [8]. As the world's largest global hospitality properties business, Marriott should have responsibly safeguarded, managed, and protected its customers' confidential information. Marriott should have undertaken appropriate steps to mitigate cybersecurity risks. Marriott's failure to protect confidential information revealed that Marriott had not behaved ethically as the global leader of the hospitality industry.

2 Technical Description of the Attack

Accenture notified Marriott of the IBM Guardium Alert on September 7, 2018 [4]. The IBM Guardium Alert was triggered by a database query from an administrative account showing the content of rows instead of the correct count of rows from a database table [4]. The content of the rows consisted of highly sensitive and critical data, including credit card numbers of hotel guests [4].

Marriott confirmed that the compromised administrative account user did not initiate the database query upon verification [4]. It is highly probable that there was indeed a cyber attack from computer criminals who triggered the IBM Guardium Alert. Once the security breach was known, Marriott immediately contacted third-party entities to initiate an information security and private incident plan to inspect records, secure information, and mitigate cybersecurity risks associated with the Marriott system and its security breach.

Computer criminals succeeded in infiltrating the SPG reservation system on July 29, 2014, as they had gradually expanded the scope of unauthorized access through common hacking methods of phishing, malware attacks, and privilege escalation. Investigators located a record of a web shell installation on devices in the SPG reservation system [13]. The devices contained an Accolade application designed to receive employee requests to modify content on the official SPG website [13]. Computer criminals gained unauthorized access to the SPG system through the web shell to view and alter confidential data in the SPG system. Upon further examination, investigators located a Remote Access Trojan (RAT) in the system nine days after the IBM Guardium Alert [4, 13].

For decades, computer hackers have been attacking computer systems with RATs to attain remote access to systems. The server sides of RATs are embedded to appear as normal files. Computer hackers send RATs through spear-phishing to trick people into downloading and installing the RAT in the system. Computer hackers could also simply perform brute-force or dictionary attacks to obtain users' passwords and eventually install a RAT to compromise the system.

Once the computer criminals succeeded in achieving remote access through RAT, they were able to

list directories displaying the critical information of each user, install malicious files to compromise data integrity, and capture keystrokes without having a real physical presence in the system. In this security breach, computer criminals could install RAT through different means. Computer criminals had unrestricted, complete, unauthorized access to the hospitality properties reservation system without an actual physical presence in the system [4, 6].

Investigators also located MimiKatz malware in the Marriott system. MimiKatz could completely bypass Multi-factor Authentication (MFA) security measures. MimiKatz had a special hash-the-pass functionality that could read data hosted in the memory of the LSASS (Local Security Authority Subsystem Service) process, as login credentials are stored in the LSASS process. Computer hackers could run MimiKatz to retrieve confidential data such as names, SHA-1 hashes, and plaintext passwords in the LSASS process.

Computer hackers could steadily obtain login credentials of users with higher administrative privileges to gain more access through MimiKatz. MimiKatz was the main malware used to achieve horizontal privilege escalation in this security breach. As computer criminals gathered login credentials of users with higher administrative privileges through MimiKatz malware, computer criminals gained restricted control and access over the hospitality properties reservation system, which allowed them to gradually gain authorized access to confidential information in the Marriott system for more than four years [4].

3 Recovery

Marriott has actively worked with third-party entities and authorities to assess the severity of data loss in this security breach. Additional actions are also being taken to minimize the potential impact of the security breach through containment and access control and to mitigate further unauthorized access from computer criminals.

Marriott has taken actions to mitigate possible cybersecurity risks in the future by removing all known malware from the Marriott system, mitigating hosts in the network, and managing user access through IP whitelisting. Furthermore, Marriott has prioritized the implementation of two-factor authentication (2FA) and isolated the most valuable data to mitigate future cyberattacks from computer criminals.

Investigators partially recovered three crucial DMP files. Computer criminals created three crucial DMP files to exfiltrate all data in a database table [13]. Computer criminals created the first DMP file, Reservation_Room_sharer.dmp, on April 15, 2015 [13]. Six days later, computer criminals created the second DMP file, Consumption_Roomtype.dmp [13]. Less than one month after creating the second DMP file, computer criminals created the third DMP file, reservation_Room_sharer.dmp [13]. Additionally, investigators uncovered more memory-scraping malware that were installed on multiple devices in the SPG system and executed on January 10, 2017, on the data management system of eight SPG hotel properties [13].

On September 19, 2018, investigators succeeded in recovering and analyzing two deleted compressed and encrypted files. Investigators were able to decrypt the two encrypted files. Those two encrypted files contained highly confidential information such as credit card numbers and passport numbers. The first encrypted file, named guest_master_profile, is an export of a database table containing credit card information of SPG customers [4]. The second encrypted file, named pp_master, is an export of a database table containing passport information of SPG customers [4].

The most crucial issue of this security breach is that computer criminals gained access to credit card numbers and passport numbers of SPG customers. On November 25 and 26, third-party investigators confirmed that computer criminals could simply make copies of those two deleted compressed and encrypted

files, as the names of the files match two tables in the SPG system [4].

Computer criminals stole a considerably large number of passport numbers and credit card numbers. Marriott concluded that computer criminals had accessed approximately 18.5 million encrypted passport numbers and 5.25 million unencrypted passport numbers [4]. The AES-128 encryption methods require two security components to decrypt the data, and both components were allegedly taken by criminals.

Computer criminals could easily obtain the master encryption keys through social engineering once they gained access to the files containing guests' passport information. Computer criminals working on behalf of China's Ministry of State Security (MSS) could easily obtain entry and exit records with those stolen passport numbers [9, 12].

Moreover, computer criminals retrieved records of 9.1 million encrypted payment card numbers and several thousand unencrypted payment card numbers [4]. Assuming the computer criminals could decrypt the files with master encryption keys, the computer criminals would have passport information of approximately 24 million SPG customers [4].

4 Human Aspects of the Problem

On November 29, 2018, Marriott notified all major credit card companies as well as relevant authorities in more than twenty countries [4]. On November 30, 2018, Marriott publicly announced that 500 million records were leaked in the security breach [4]. Two months later, they adjusted the number of leaked records to 383 million [4]. The merging of SPG, Ritz Carlton, and Marriott accounts did not finish until December 18, 2018 [4].

Due to lax and insufficient monitoring, the Marriott security breach was not known until the IBM Guardium Alert appeared [5, 13]. Computer criminals would have had even longer, more coveted access to that highly confidential data without the IBM Guardium Alert that was triggered by a database query. This IBM Guardium Alert prompted an extensive investigation to evaluate the nature and full extent of damages from this security breach.

In this Marriott security breach, computer criminals succeeded in obtaining millions of both encrypted and decrypted credit card numbers and passport numbers. Marriott speculated that some of the records were duplicated; consequently, the actual number of compromised records was substantially smaller than the official record of 500 million [4]. Marriott purported that the security breach yielded substantially fewer negative social consequences, as some of the stolen credit card information had expired. Nevertheless, much of the highly confidential data could be used for harassment, blackmail, and victimization.

Marriott claimed that it is nearly impossible to ordinarily pass through immigration in a country without a physical passport; thus, computer criminals could not accomplish any significant task with only passport numbers of hotel guests. Criminals could undertake countless illicit activities without owning physical passports. For instance, computer criminals could track and trace people entering or exiting any air, land, or sea border with passport numbers. For this reason, passport numbers are highly confidential data that should not be in the hands of computer criminals.

Relevant law enforcement authorities have been working with Marriott to monitor the Dark Web, and thus far, no records of stolen data from the Marriott system have been found for sale. Around December 2018, American intelligence agencies publicly reported that the computer criminals were working on behalf of the Chinese Ministry of State Security (MSS), a standard form of espionage [9]. The criminal activities strongly resembled possible intelligence collection from the Ministry of State Security (MSS) in China [9]. Neither

Marriott nor SPG took appropriate actions to mitigate potential risks. As a result, computer criminals stole millions of passport numbers and credit card numbers on behalf of the Chinese Government.

Marriott competed against other business entities, such as the Intercontinental Hotel Group (IHG) and the Chinese insurance company Anbang, to acquire Starwood Hotels. Marriott bid \$79.53 per share after Anbang bid \$78 per share [12]. Marriott outbid Anbang to acquire SPG, and coincidentally, the security breach was strongly linked to espionage activities from China. American intelligence agencies also revealed that the stolen passport numbers were exploited for gathering data in the form of security intelligence [9, 12].

After the ninth-largest security breach of the 21st century, there was another security breach in early 2020 [3]. In the most recent Marriott security breach, computer criminals succeeded in gaining unauthorized access to Marriott using login credentials of two employees at a franchise property to steal confidential data such as addresses, dates of birth, points balances, elite status, and account numbers of hotel and airline loyalty programs of 5.2 million hotel guests [3].

Marriott could have performed significantly more actions to defend, protect, and safeguard those records from computer criminals, but Marriott chose not to act and behave appropriately upon the merger and acquisition with SPG. Computer criminals were able to exploit the stolen passport numbers for intelligence purposes and to gain information about the physical locations of government officials and business executives, which potentially jeopardized the livelihood and safety of millions of people around the globe.

5 Ethical and Legal Considerations

Marriott's misuse of data was an infringement of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Marriott was heavily fined for data misuse due to their failure to take proper due diligence in the merger and acquisition of SPG. The United Kingdom led the investigation against Marriott for infringement of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). On July 9, 2019, the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO) sent a Notice of Intent to fine Marriott £99,200,396 for infringement of the GDPR pursuant to section 155(1) DPA and Schedule 16 of the DPA (the "NOI") [10].

Furthermore, the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO) raised the issue with Marriott pertaining to the 72-hour breach notification rules written under the Notification to the supervisory authority in Article 33 of the GDPR because the ICO was not notified of the security breach until November 22, 2018 [10, 13]. As a result of the Notice of Intent of the infringements, on August 23, 2019, Marriott made the first written formal representation to the Notice of Intent [10].

On December 6, 2019, the ICO offered Marriott the option to make additional representations under a new deadline set forth by the ICO [10]. On December 17, 2019, Marriott accepted the new deadline of March 30, 2020 [10]. On December 20, 2019, the ICO sent Marriott a draft of the Penalty Notice [10]. On January 31, 2020, Marriott made the second written formal representation. After the second representation, there was an agreement to extend the deadline to June 1, 2020 [10].

On April 3, 2020, the ICO invited Marriott to make further representations regarding the fiscal impact caused by the Covid-19 pandemic. On April 17, 2020, Marriott responded to the message that pertained to the Covid-19 pandemic. On October 30, 2020, the ICO issued a monetary fine of £18,400,000 against Marriott for infringement of the GDPR pursuant to Article 5(1)(f) and Article 32 GDPR [10]. Marriott bought cyber insurance to cover the heavy fine; hence, Marriott paid less than £1 million [8, 10].

The Information Commissioner's Office (ICO) finally penalized Marriott for approximately £18 million,

but after the reduction of the fine, Marriott had only paid less than 20% of what the ICO first issued due to legal representations, prompt investigations, and the economic impact of the Covid-19 pandemic [8, 10]. Marriott paid only the deductible, which is less than £1 million, for the infringements of EU regulations for the ninth-largest security breach of the 21st century [8]. The fine did not impact Marriott's revenue. Marriott suffered no fiscal deficit even though 500 million confidential records are now in the hands of computer criminals working for the Ministry of State Security (MSS) in China [8, 9].

Class-action lawsuits and group litigation were filed against Marriott. A class-action lawsuit was filed against Marriott in the London High Court by millions of customers [7]. Hundreds of class-action lawsuits have been filed against Marriott for negligence, negligence per se, breach of confidence, and deceptive trade practices by private businesses and government entities [7].

Under the GDPR, Accenture, the processor, is liable for handling, monitoring, and processing data for Marriott, the controller [7]. Class-action lawsuits were also filed against Accenture. Accenture was accused of not having adequate security measures to mitigate and identify any security risk by the plaintiffs [11]. Accenture publicly disavowed such accusations and responded that those cases were filed without merit, as Marriott is a very important client of Accenture [11].

Marriott and Accenture behaved in an unprofessional manner regarding how they handled the ethical implications and legal framework of the security breach. Marriott bought cyber insurance to handle the legality of the security breach, and since the day of the IBM Guardium Alert, Marriott had been working with insurance companies to assess cyber insurance coverage [8].

6 Future-proofing

The Information Commissioner's Office (ICO) issued the second-largest fine against Marriott for infringement of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and hundreds of lawsuits were filed against Marriott for negligence and unfair trade practices [13]. Marriott could have played a more effective role in mitigating cybersecurity risks after the ninth-largest security breach of the 21st century.

Marriott could have done more to mitigate cybersecurity risks related to broken authentication. Marriott could have implemented Multi-factor Authentication (MFA) to prevent computer criminals from performing brute-force or dictionary attacks on the system. Marriott could also require all users in the Marriott system to set up high-entropy passwords against sensitive data exposure. SPG should never have created an application that permitted employees to request changes to the official SPG website. Computer criminals could easily exploit the vulnerability of broken access control. In this Marriott security breach, computer criminals installed a web shell and obtained millions of pieces of confidential information because computer criminals knew the weaknesses in the SPG and Marriott systems.

One of the most important cybersecurity techniques is to act as though the systems have already been compromised by computer attackers. Computer criminals often target systems with sensitive data. It is not necessary for Marriott to store sensitive data such as passport numbers in their systems. All passport numbers and credit card numbers should be securely encrypted, and the system should be properly configured so that computer criminals should never be able to decrypt that confidential information. In the future, Marriott could prevent this dilemma by declining to collect passport numbers of guests in the system, as the majority of guests have no desire to let Marriott know their passport numbers.

Insufficient monitoring is one of the top reasons that a security breach could easily happen. Numerous malware instances in the system went unnoticed for more than four years. The lax monitoring of privileged

accounts and databases indicated that Marriott had not been frequently performing assessments on the vulnerabilities of the reservation system. Marriott could prevent this dilemma by simply assuming the system is already compromised. One of the reasons that computer criminals were able to infiltrate the system is that there was a security misconfiguration related to user permissions. No users should have permissions to perform unnecessary tasks. Employees should not be allowed to request changes to the official SPG website.

Marriott encrypted passport numbers and credit card numbers with outdated AES-128 encryption methods. Chinese computer criminals have the means to decrypt the encrypted files containing passport numbers and credit card numbers of customers. Computer criminals have access to encrypted data that was encrypted with the AES-128 encryption method in the Marriott system. Marriott could have actively assessed and monitored the system, as well as ensured that all confidential data was isolated and encrypted for the merger of accounts with SPG.

Marriott did not follow the ethical guidance under the Open Data Institute's Data Ethics Canvas. Marriott could have designed extensive, compulsory training for employees and users in the Marriott system against social engineering. Marriott could formulate comprehensive physical and computer training for all employees irrespective of account privileges, considering that the most recent Marriott security breach happened due to the accounts of two employees in a Marriott franchise property.

In the future, Marriott should play an active role in preventing any unauthorized access to the Marriott system instead of outsourcing the monitoring of the system to Accenture. Computer criminals stole additional confidential data by using the login credentials of two Marriott franchise property employees in early 2020. Computer criminals should never be able to obtain users' login credentials. Marriott should also design in-depth training for employees to detect social engineering.

7 Conclusions

Marriott took actions to contain known malware, mitigate further cybersecurity risks, and investigate the ninth-largest security breach of the 21st century. Marriott's actions reflected how they viewed computer ethics. The CEO of Marriott, Arne Sorenson, testified on behalf of Marriott before the United States Senate. Sorenson apologized for the gravity of the Marriott security breach merging with the SPG reservation system, and he admitted that Marriott did not undertake adequate security measures and due diligence before the merger and acquisition of SPG [4].

Marriott could have taken appropriate actions to mitigate cybersecurity risks before the merging of accounts. On the contrary, Marriott had unethically depended on buying cyber insurance to minimize the fiscal blow instead of acknowledging the social impact stemming from the enormity of data loss. Marriott did not prioritize its ethical responsibility to protect confidential data from exploitation for nefarious and intelligence purposes by computer criminals. Marriott is a for-profit global hospitality properties business, and its end goal is to generate revenue by charging customers for staying at their hospitality properties. To stay at some of their properties, customers are required to leave records of passport and credit card information.

The failures of Marriott to safeguard the system and mitigate cybersecurity risks led to hundreds of millions of stolen passports and credit card numbers being exploited for nefarious means by Chinese computer criminals working on behalf of the Chinese Government. The CEO and leadership team of Marriott prioritized profits over ethical principles. Marriott earned more than billions in net income each year. Marriott did not demonstrate appropriate concern for the ethics of leaking customers' private information. Instead,

Marriott deliberately prepared to apply cyber insurance to resolve potential fines as they committed to earning more profits and revenues by charging guests for staying at Marriott's vast collection of worldwide hospitality properties. The consequences of breaking the GDPR are severe. However, Marriott was not sufficiently penalized for breaking the GDPR.

The repeated occurrence of security breaches in the Marriott system indicated that the world's largest global hospitality properties business has not acted in an appropriate and professional manner to mitigate cybersecurity risks. In consideration of another security breach that happened in early 2020, there is substantial evidence that computer criminals succeeded in obtaining highly critical and confidential unencrypted data including names, physical addresses, email addresses, phone numbers, company names, linked airline loyalty program numbers, hotel loyalty program numbers, hotel loyalty elite status, gender, dates of birth, room preferences, credit card information, and passport numbers of more than a few hundred million hotel guests [3, 4, 6].

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